

ENHANCING ENERGY MANAGEMENT BY FLC BASED CONTROLLER BASED HYBRID POWER SYSTEM FED MICROGRID

B ARUNA, C RAMEAH BABU, C SUMALATHA,
ASSISTANT PROFESSOR ^{1,2,3}

bonasiaruna@gmail.com, ramesh.babu224@gmail.com, sumalathac@svitatp.ac.in

Department of EEE, Sri Venkateswara Institute of Technology,
N.H 44, Hampapuram, Raphthadu, Anantapuramu, Andhra Pradesh 515722

ABSTRACT: This research proposes an effective approach for managing energy in a microgrid that uses a combination of wind, solar, and batteries on a small scale. In order to put a hybrid microgrid through its paces, engineers have created systems that convert wind and solar energy into usable forms, as well as battery storage, power electronic converters, control algorithms, and controllers. An energy management system maintains the power balance regardless of changes in renewable energy power production or changes in load demand. Various control algorithms, energy management systems, and test conditions may be run on this microgrid's standalone mode. To evaluate and test the control algorithms of the microgrid system simulator, rapid control prototyping is used to execute real-time control. Research and testing of algorithms in smart grid applications may be conducted on the suggested small-scale renewable energy based microgrid.

KEYWORDS: Energy management, microgrids, renewable power sources

INTRODUCTION: Proposals for renewable energy systems that can power themselves have been advanced on a worldwide scale. Because of this first step, renewable power producing systems have emerged, allowing for the production of electricity independently via the integration of many renewable energy sources. Solar and wind power are the two most popular hybrid renewable energy sources. Since none of these energy sources is

inherently reliable, an energy storage system (ESS) is often used in standalone applications. There are a number of methods used to regulate and provide effective power transmission in hybrid renewable energy systems. System design is highly dependent on energy conversion system type and converter type utilised at various points in the system; this topic has drawn a lot of attention from technical experts. The performance of a hybrid energy system was evaluated using meteorological data and several real-world load demand roles. Energy management in both grid-connected and freestanding modes is covered in the context of the smartgrid control system simulation. The control of the state of charge (SOC) is tested in a virtualized wind-solar-battery ESS system. An improved DC grid hardware prototype with a scaled-down system for controlling state-of-charge (SOC) batteries

regulation of voltage for independent DC The smartgrid model was created. We built a hardware prototype of a cheap hybrid standalone power generating device. A smartgrid that uses a combination of renewable energy sources, such as wind, solar, and batteries, is the focus of this study. The smartgrid's power balance may be maintained with the help of an energy management system that offers flexible and adaptable control over a range of situations including changes in renewable energy sources and variations in load demand. Using fast control prototyping,

the suggested system may be evaluated in a real-time setting. These methods enable the development of efficient power in renewable energy management systems by allowing the testing of control algorithms in real time. Within well-defined limits, a microgrid consists of several interconnected loads and dispersed energy resources that act as a single, unified entity that can be controlled in relation to the larger grid. Microgrids have the ability to switch between grid linked and island mode operation. Microgrids are distributed power systems that employ a number of smaller generators, often in the sub megawatt range, to provide electricity to tens to thousands of consumers. Enhanced power quality, dependability, security, and flexibility of power sources are the main benefits of smart grid. Smartgrid systems' advantages cover a lot of ground, making it hard to apply the cost-per-watt viewpoint. However, it should be mentioned that the initial investment in smartgrid may be rather high, which is why it is most effective when implemented as a community project. The advanced features of smart grid

than microgrid it provides electricity network that is used by digital and some of the technologies to monitor in real time and control the electricity from generation sources. It also provides high protection and security features. Once in place the cost of upgrading or it can replace significantly one or more of power sources with less capital intensity centralized power grid generator. As they generally it cannot provide power over vast distances, smartgrids are ideal for renewable energy generation integration. Another advantage is to have dissimilar forms that it is possible of generation. For example, a microgrid power system can use wind power, to gain the advantages of both fortify generating ability. A smartgrid offer a higher level of security, and the limited body of affected, making them less appealing

target for hostile intensions.

Through the comprehensive analysis of previous and related literature, this study offers several implications for both researchers and policymakers regarding RE development. Researchers need to focus more on factors influencing the intention of people in using RE. Moreover, there is a definite need to conduct more research that incorporates RES using public opinion, which can assist to reduce reservations among the public and promote future use of RES and RET. The government can make plans to expand RE concepts and introduce study of this topic in secondary schools and higher levels of education. A variety of RET should be available through government policies and incentives. It is evident that for the development of RET, government and research and development (R&D) programs play a vital role. In the case of industry, the

By considering public opinion, politicians may craft enticing policies that include the chosen RES. Some possible solutions to these problems include raising public knowledge of RES and RET use, for example. Introducing welfare programmes linked to RE projects is another significant practical consequence for politicians and the public sector in order to get a good reaction from the people. There will be far-reaching consequences for universities. One such area that might be involved in RE initiatives is the academic sector. It would be crucial to hold seminars where students from different fields may learn about RES and RET in this situation. Also, the study stresses how important it is to gauge public sentiment in order to provide future academics with data they may use to successfully implement RE. Renewable energy (RE) is becoming an issue that both professionals and the broader public are interested in. Both the total and relative numbers of studies focusing on RES have grown in recent years. It is possible to meet the present electricity demands of an existing community by installing a smartgrid system. Because of the high costs and complexity of implementing such a system on a massive central power grid, these benefits are simply not feasible. Through the use of interconnection, many smartgrids may form a "cluster" that allows for the pooling of resources while each one retains its own autonomy and security. Energy is now produced closer to its points of consumption as a result of both rising demand and rethinking of power networks. This power is

produced by renewable resources, the cost of which is continuing to decline, making them more competitive. This is particularly true for wind and photovoltaic solar energy. In order to upgrade the current power grid to the smart grid of the future, smartgrids will be indispensable. To put it simply, they are networks that distribute power at low voltage and include renewable energy sources (RESs), backup controlled energy sources (generators, for example), storage, and adjustable loads.

They may lessen the load on power plants and improve grid dependability by connecting the aforementioned components to it. There has been a lot of continuing research on power and energy management systems (EMS), which are crucial components of smartgrid control. EMS can regulate the use of controllable loads, deploy the active power of RES, and run controllable generators appropriately. Smart grids have the capability to function either in conjunction with the main grid or independently. The main grid regulates the voltage and frequency in grid-connected mode. A smartgrid's job, instead of ensuring end-user power supply (because to the main grid's high availability), will be to utilise its energy management system (EMS) to inject energy into the main grid when prices are high and purchase it when prices are low. In addition, microgrids that are linked to the main grid provide a more efficient method of connecting RESs to the grid, which might increase their energy output. Because of the high reliance on weather and environment, hybrid systems are often the best option.

renewable energy system with battery storage systems. The hybrid energy systems are typically used for electricity supply several applications such as houses or farms in rural areas without grid extension, telecommunication antennas, and equipment, and many other standalone systems. In many cases these hybrid systems simply the highest reliability and lowest costs compared to systems with only one energy source.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM:

The goal of this project is to create a microgrid that uses renewable energy sources such as wind, solar, and batteries on a small scale. Solar and wind power are two of the most common types of hybrid renewable energy. Given their unreliability and unpredictability, none of these energy sources can be relied on to consistently provide a steady stream of power. To lessen power fluctuations and improve dependability on

load demand, a battery is included as a benefit in this scenario. In order to ensure that energy is produced and distributed at the lowest possible cost, it is recommended to implement an energy management system. This system will offer the required functionality. It enables the tracking of energy resources in real-time. For adaptable outcomes, it engages with different load demand fluctuation situations. A battery storage system is suggested to assist renewable energy sources based on solar and wind. Additionally, the DC bus is linked to their converters. If the wind is not enough, you may connect the PV panels to the grid. Connect to the grid and use batteries if PV doesn't cut it. So, for example, if the output has to be compatible with the AC grid, the rectifier's DC output may be converted to AC, and the result is same.

for PV and battery. It is used for both AC/DC grid is the main advantage.

For making this we have to implement EMS algorithm. An energy management system is proposed to maintain distribution of power in microgrid and provides a stable output and flexible control for different variations of load demand.

The proposed system can be tested in real time environment. It allows real time monitoring of energy resources. It interacts with various scenarios of load demand variations for flexible results. It checks for validation of algorithm at real time and it implements energy efficient renewable energy management systems.

- a. In any natural conditions it satisfies the load demand because of EMS.
- b. Reliability is high by preventing disturbances in frequency and power flow.
- c. This is bidirectional system because the battery charging and dis-charging takes place.

Fig 2.1(b):Components of small-scale wind-solar-battery microgrid with EMS.

2.2 Methodology:

- 3 Figure 2.1(b) depicts the system design. Part one consists of a solar energy conversion system; part two consists of a wind energy conversion system; and part three consists of a battery storage system. renewable energy sources such as solar panels and wind turbines linked to a DC bus via a battery storage system and the converters that power them.
 - ii) for single-phase loads and the load-side inverter
 - iii) A controller that operates in real-time and incorporates the energy management system.

One component of the wind energy conversion system is a wind turbine that is based on permanent magnet synchronous generators (PMSGs). Maximum power point tracking (MPPT) is used to run the solar photovoltaic (PV) panels when the combined power output of the wind and PV is insufficient to meet the load demand. The maximum power point tracking (MPPT) system is activated when the amount of power produced exceeds the amount needed. It is deactivated when charging the battery becomes too risky. The energy balance of the system is maintained by means of the battery storage system. In order to govern

the flow of power to the load via a single-phase inverter, an energy management system is used in various situations. SEC System for Solar Energy Conversion 2.2.1

One way to harness the sun's rays and turn them into usable energy is via a solar energy conversion system. There will be no emissions of greenhouse gases, and it won't pollute the environment either. The process of generating energy from solar radiation is known as solar power. A solar photovoltaic (PV) panel, a DC-DC boost converter, and a maximum power point tracking (MPPT) controller make up the SECS, as seen in the figure below. Whenever the MPPT is dependent on the battery storage system's level of charge,

functioning either in multi-period power-saving mode or in non-MPPT mode. Renewable energy sources like solar power are endless. Less distortion is seen in solar cells. Almost little upkeep is necessary.

Figure 2.2.1 displays the P-V characteristics of the solar panel as a function of irradiance effect, with irradiance values ranging from 400 W/m² to 1200 W/m² and a constant temperature of 25°C. At 17.6 V, the maximum power for 1000 W/m² is 66Wp.

Fig 2.2.1(a): Solar energy conversion system with controller

Fig 2.2.1(b): Effect of irradiance on PV array performance

3.2.1 Wind Energy Conversion System (WECS)

4 The purpose of wind energy conversion systems is to transform the mechanical energy contained in wind into usable form. As the airflow enters, it transforms the kinetic energy into mechanical power that is then

transformed into electrical power.

A basic idea underlies the operation of wind turbines. Powering the batteries, a DC generator transforms wind energy into direct current. The wind turbines' main function is to harness the kinetic energy of the wind and transform it into mechanical work by means of rotation. Wind turbines harness the kinetic energy of the wind and transform it into electrical current by use of specially engineered blades. The renewable and non-polluting energy source is wind power. The wind turbine, PMSG, DC-DC boost converter, and controller make up the three primary components of the WECS. The air density, in kg/m³, the rotor blades area, in m²/s, and the wind speed, in m/s, are the primary wind-based characteristics of a wind turbine. The power coefficient C_p is determined by the parameters TSR (tip speed ratio) and θ (pitch angle). (2.2.2) This system makes use of a variable-speed wind turbine. In Figure 2.2.2, we can see the wind turbine design; for different wind speeds and pitch angles, the coefficient is denoted as C_p . Because of its cheap running costs and minimal maintenance requirements, a permanent magnet synchronous generator is chosen. Providing utility grid with alternate current (AC) electricity is the PMSG's job. Wind speed affects the generator's output. There are more poles

on a PMSG, making it more competitive and helpful for low speed wind turbine drives. Reliability, increased power density, and maximum efficiency are just

a few of the benefits of using PMSG. Wind turbines that use PMSG more

effective. The generator's three-phase output is first filtered to remove any alternating current, then converted to direct current using a diode rectifier. A DC-DC boost converter subsequently raises the voltage.

Fig 2.2.2(a): wind energy conversion system with controller

Fig 2.1.2(b): Mechanical characteristics of wind turbine for different wind speeds.

4.2.1 Battery Storage System (BSS)

Battery energy storage systems are rechargeable battery systems that store energy from solar arrays or the electric grid and provide that energy to a home or business because they contain advanced technology that regular batteries cannot perform. Battery energy storage system works by converting the DC energy being produced by solar panels and storing it as

AC power for later use. The batteries store energy and when there is a need of energy, they can quickly release the energy in to the grid. This makes power supply more predictable. The energy stored in the batteries can be used also in when it is needed when more electricity required. It has low environmental

Fig 2.2.3: Battery energy storage system with controller.

The BSS has two parts a lead acid battery and a bidirectional DC-DC buck-boost converter. This converter takes the responsibility for maintaining the voltage in DC bus through a PI controller as shown in Fig 2.2.3. The Parameters of BSS are where Q , is the battery capacity coefficient and I_{bat} is the current of battery. It has two modes of operation they are; charging and discharging, this depends on the power generated by both solar and wind. The battery also operates in these two modes based on the energy constraints which are determined by the SOC limits.

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battery storage system from economic point of view. The power is controlled by an energy management system for the variations of renewable energy power generation and also for the load demand variations. It allows realtime monitoring of consumption energy resources. The application of this system is to provide electricity for commercial loads such as industries, residential loads likes homes and to prove electrical energy for traction.

4.2.4 Operation

The main operation is boost converter of solar energy conversion system operates in two modes depending on the power generation; they are MPPT mode/ off-MPPT mode. The Battery bidirectional converter operates in two modes charging or discharging mode and keeps the DC bus voltage at constant, the DC-DC boost converter of the wind energy conversion system operates in boost mode. The power in the microgrid must be balanced and controlled under different generation of power from renewable energy sources and load demand conditions. The power balance equation is given as follows

$$P_w + P_{pv} = P_L + P_{bat} \text{ -----2.2.5}$$

The different modes of operation of the Energy management system are presented in the flowchart

$$SOC_{min} \leq SOC \leq SOC_{max} \text{ ---- (3.2.3)}$$

4.2.2 Load Side Control

The DC microgrid is connected to a single-phase resistive load through a single-phase inverter with a controller the undesired harmonic content. An R-L filter used at the inverter output to filter. The outer loop PI controller is used to regulate the voltage and the inner loop PI controller regulates the current.

A single-phase inverter converts a DC input into a AC output. The input of the inverter is a fixed DC voltage which is nominally obtained from the batteries and the output of the inverter is generally fixed or variable frequency alternating voltage, the AC voltage magnitude is also variable. It is energy efficient.

2.2.4(a) Inverter:

Inverter is used to convert DC output of PV unit to AC power.

2.2.4(b) Grid:

Output power of inverter is given to the nearby electrical grid for the power generation.

2.2.4(c) MPPT:

In order to utilize the maximum power produced by the PV modules, the power conversion equipment has to be equipped with a maximum power point tracker (MPPT). It is a device which tracks the voltage at where the maximum power is utilized at all times.

4.2.3 Energy Management System (EMS)

For reliable and stable operation of microgrid with multiple DGs, coordinated control of energy management system is proposed. An energy management system is proposed to maintain power distribution in microgrid and provides a functionality which gives configurable and flexible control in different scenarios of load demand variations. It allows optimizing a

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 EMS(energy management system) allows optimizing a battery energy storage system from economic point of view.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The developed methodology is used to project a hybrid renewable energy sources solar PV-Wind-Battery. This section demonstrates the effectiveness of proposed methodology by means of implication of hybrid renewable energy sources with EMS. Inputs of the project are solar radiation, ambient temperature, and wind speed resource, battery voltage and capacity. Load demand changes according to the period of the variations in temperature. For the purposes of validating the model performance, the proposed system is simulated with MATLAB V 7.7 that will also be employed as a software tool during optimization. The simulation for the proposed system has been developed with MATLAB/Simulink model.

Fig 2.2.5: Flowchart for operating Energymanagement system

In energy management system there are four modes of operation. Each mode of operation depends on two conditions; one is the generation of power and second is the state of charge of battery how much it consumed. The desired mode of operation is done when it has the amount of power generation from the SECS and WECS is more than the load demand. During this operation, the battery is charged until SOCmax, if the SOC of the battery reaches SOCmax, then the MPPT controller is switched to off-mode and this decreases the solar power generation of solar power. If the total power generation is more than the demand and the excess generated power it is not used for long period of time to charge the battery and any further power requirement at the load is now supplied by the battery. When the power generated by the solar and wind energy sources it do not meet the load demand, the power deficit is supplied by the battery until the SOC reaches SOCmin, once this is reached then load shedding needs to done in order to maintain power balance as the power supply is less than demand.

Fig3 (a): Schematic of Simulink diagram

Resource data were calculated using mean solar radiation and wind speed and capacity of battery and the results are shown in below figures. The objective of the first case is to deliver a constant power to the load for different generating conditions. The solar irradiance is varied by the lamps switching on/off and thus providing various irradiance levels. The PV module input in

DC form is stepped up in boost converter and fed to inverter to form an AC output. The irradiance is varied by 1000W/m², 800W/m², 400W/m² and 600W/m² at the start, 20s, 30s and 50s respectively as shown in fig 3.1 (a). the x-axis indicates the time while y-axis represents the irradiance.

4.1 Variations in Renewable Energy Sources with Constant Load

Fig 3.1(a): solar irradiance levels
Energy of wind is a source that is

friendly to the environment. Its converting wind kinetic energy into mechanical energy, and the magnitude of this mechanical energy that has been converted depends on the wind speed and air density. The generator speed for different variations of wind speed is shown in fig 3.1(b). The wind speed was varied by 12m/s, 8 m/s, 11m/s, 7 m/s and 11 m/s at the start, 10s, 20s, 40s and 60s respectively. Where x-axis is time and y-axis is speed.

Fig 3.1(b): wind speed levels.

Fig 3.1(c): DC bus voltage for constant load with variable renewable energy sources

The DC voltage is maintained constant at 50V by energy storage device for
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controlling balance of power with variable renewable sources of energy as shown in Fig.3.1(c). where x-axis is time and y-axis is voltage for DC.

There are many kinds of variable speed generators used in wind turbine. Particularly, PMSG is direct drive, has slow rotation speed, does not have rotor current. Therefore, the pitch angle is controlled to catch the maximum coefficient at rate 13 m/s wind speed. After 0.14s, the generator-side inverter are co-operated to control the voltage through controllers. One of the main sources of renewable energy for future demand may be a wind energy generation system. The generator speed for different variations of wind speed is shown in Fig. 3.1(d) where x-axis is time and y-axis is speed of generation.

Fig 3.1(d): PMSG speed for constant load with variable renewable energy sources

The high efficiency and low maintenance will reduce the cost that is the important to invest. When wind turbine catches the wind speed at rate 4m/s, PMSG

begins to operate. The power at different locations of the microgrid for constant load with variable renewable energy sources is shown in below figure. Where x-axis is time and y-axis is speed of generator.

Fig 3.1(e) PMSG power

In RES the PV system or solar powersystem is a system designed to supply solar power by means of photovoltaics as shown in fig below. Where x-axis is time and y-axis is power of PV.

Fig 3.1(f): PV power

Power capacity is how much energy is stored in the battery the voltage that battery provides multiplied by current where x-axis is time and y-axis is power of battery as shown in below fig.3.1(g).

Fig 3.1(g): battery power

The amount of power is generated by solar and wind energy conversions systems increases the load demand of battery from 0 to 10sec of time. Then after completion of 10sec discharging of battery starts and at level of discharge varies at various instants depending on the differences in lower of power from the renewable energy sources. Where x-axis is time and y-axis is power of battery. in fig 3.1(g).

Fig 3.1(h): load power

Load power is the part of the output of an electric power used for operation of motors or heating devices. The electrical load may be resistive, inductive, capacitive. The electric load indicates the power passing through the line or machine. The nature of load depends on load factor, power factor of the system. Where x-axis is time and y-axis is power of load as shown in fig 3.1(h).

Fig 3.1(i): State of charge of battery for constant load with variable renewable energy sources.

When at particular time at constant load the power of battery seems to be low and the state of battery charging is clearly charges and discharges as shown in fig3.1(i). where x-axis is time and y-axis is SOC(%).

For some occurrences the load voltage falls marginally as the battery discharge rate is higher between 40sec to 60sec of time when the voltage is constant at load as shown in fig 3.1(j).where x-axis is time and y-axis is power of load.

Fig 3.1(j): load voltage

3.2. Variations in Load with Constant Renewable Energy Sources

Solar irradiance is rate at which radiant energy is incident on unit area of the surface found by integration of irradiance over particular time. In the case second, the generation of solar power is kept constant with the solar irradiance kept constant at 800W/m² as shown in Fig. 3.2(a). where x-axis is time and y-axis is irradiation.

Fig 4.2(a): solar irradiance levels

PV-Wind-battery-hybrid power system directly converts solar and wind resources to electricity. In this case second wind power generation is kept constant wind speed is constant at 11m/s as shown in Fig.3.2(b) where x-axis is time and y-axis is speed of wind.

Fig 3.2(b) wind speed levels

The balancing of generated power is achieved by the energy storage device that maintains DC bus voltage at constant at voltage of 50 as shown in Fig. 3.2(c). where x-axis is time and y-axis is DC voltage.

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Fig 3.2(c): DC bus voltage for constant renewable energy sources with variable load.

The speed of PMSG for constant renewable sources with variable load. At speed of 5280 rpm the generator speed is constant as the wind speed is maintained constant shown in Fig. 3.2(d). where x-axis is time and y-axis is speed of generator.

IV. CONCLUSION

An innovative microgrid powered by a combination of solar, wind, and batteries is created and put into operation with the help of a smart grid-based energy management system. The efficacy of the suggested energy management system was tested experimentally for various combinations of renewable energy sources and load demands. Fast control prototyping in controller was used to create the control algorithms and energy management system. The system's adaptability to fluctuating renewable energy sources and loads is shown by the testing findings. A well-functioning energy management system is made possible by the controller. Researchers in the area of smart-grid systems for hybrid renewable energy may use this system as a foundation to test various control algorithms and case situations in the future.

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